

Refining Design Approaches and Implementing the Material Matrix Assessment to Foster Structural Components Circularity

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Abstract. Integrating eco-design strategies is crucial when developing sustainable structural components. In the automotive industry, eco-design strategies are becoming essential as the industry faces pressure to reduce its carbon footprint and comply with regulations to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Integrating these strategies into vehicles' design and manufacturing processes can significantly improve resource efficiency and reduce emissions, e.g. using lightweight and recyclable materials, such as aluminium, carbon fibre composites, and bio-based plastics, can enhance fuel efficiency and minimise energy consumption. Consequently, refining the eco-design strategies can participate in shifting from traditional linear production into circular design, i.e., using design for repair, reuse, refurbishment, and recycling approaches can limit the generation of waste products and reduce the pressure on the environment by reducing the need to extract raw materials. Several studies explained the best approach to selecting the proper design strategies, and more needs to be done on how the design strategies can be applied to support product circularity. It is crucial to understand that implementing eco-design strategies is challenging, and the main challenge is that product designers and manufacturers need knowledge and awareness. Consequently, incentives to implement eco-design strategies are still immature, and many companies focus on short-term profits rather than long-term sustainability. The archival value of this report is to:

- Define tactics and general circular design approaches (DFX) to preserve structural components and materials integrity.
- Guide designers while considering the product circularity and end of life (EOL).
- Provide an illustrative way to select the best material for the component based on a decision from the material matrix assessment.

Keywords: Design Approaches – Structural component circularity – Material Matrix Assessment – Automotive Industry – Carbon footprint.

1 Introduction

Eco-design involves integrating environmental considerations into product design to minimize the environmental impact throughout the product's lifecycle [1]. This includes extracting raw materials, manufacturing, distributing, using, and end-of-life disposal. Designers must consider the product's impact on the environment, such as greenhouse gas emissions, energy consumption, and waste generation, and identify areas where improvements can be made [2, 3]. Many authors have classified and identified strategies, methods, and tools that support product design for facilitating the transition to eco-design. These studies have emphasised the vast and diverse range of supporting approaches and the criteria for selecting the most appropriate eco-design approach [4-6]. Additionally, implementing eco-design strategies can directly improve crashworthiness and vibration performance through proper structure design optimisation. This involves optimising the size, shape, and topology of developed components to reduce material use and enhance structural performance [7].

The automotive sector is under pressure to diminish its carbon footprint to keep up with the EU Fit for 55 and zero carbon by 2050 goals. It has been estimated that up to 80% of all environmental impacts are determined during the design phase of products. That is why the refinement and development of Eco-design strategies and assessments are vital to the industry. Some popular strategies vehicle manufacturers usually rely on are using lighter materials [8], design of assembly/disassembly [3], and designing for remanufacturability [9].

The main challenge in eco-design is the need for product designers and manufacturers to have the right knowledge and awareness. This article aims to help end-users and designers tailor and streamline their approaches by providing guidelines and support in choosing the best circular design for their application.

2 Eco-Design Approaches

The typology of eco-design approaches encompasses diverse strategies and principles aimed at reducing the environmental impact of products and systems. **Fig. 1** represents the most straightforward framework. These approaches can be broadly categorised into several key themes. One prevalent approach is related to preserving the product's integrity, and the other is keeping the material's integrity.

2.1 Design for Preserving Product Integrity

Product integrity was defined for the first time as the extent to which a product remains identical under the loads encountered during its life cycle [10]. A design approach for longevity, life span extension, and recovery should be applied to maintain product integrity.

The design approach for longevity involves evaluating a product's life cycle to ensure a long lifespan, considering user needs, business objectives, and resource efficiency [10]. Physical durability is crucial, influenced by factors like wear, fatigue, and

corrosion, all addressed through strategies such as design for reliability and durability [5, 11, 12]. Designing for life extension in the automotive industry includes choosing robust materials, optimizing maintenance, and adhering to standards like EN 13306:2018 for maintenance types [13]. Maintenance relies on strategies like design for Assembly and Disassembly to facilitate accessibility and reduce costs [3]. Design for recovery aims to salvage economic and ecological value, with options like repair, refurbishing, and recycling considered to maintain product and material integrity [14].

Fig. 1. Typology for design approaches. The chart also shows an example of related DFX strategies that should be implemented.

2.2 Design for Preserving Materials Integrity

Materials integrity significantly contributes to the safety and environmental success of any product/vehicle circularity. Design for recyclability is the leading player in preserving product material integrity and is a crucial eco-design strategy that aims to reduce product environmental impact throughout the product life cycle.

3 Considered Aspects of Eco-design

Incorporating environmental considerations into product development and redesign is a practice known as eco-design. Eco-design aims to balance ecological and economic requirements by systematically addressing environmental aspects at every stage of the product development process. Its overarching goal is to create products that minimise their environmental impact across the entire product life cycle. Within the framework of eco-design, various design alternatives that align with specific targets and constraints can be evaluated. This evaluation process aligns with eco-design principles emphasising sustainable practices and environmental responsibility. As indicated in **Fig. 2**, the environmental footprint assessment encompasses various stages of a product's life

cycle, including the production phase, use phase, and end-of-life options such as recycling or landfilling. These aspects are integral to the holistic assessment of a product's environmental impact.

Fig. 2. Product System, showing different vehicle production phases and Eco-design strategies that can be implanted to shift from linear to circular production.

The Production Phase includes critical elements such as raw material extraction, manufacturing of the structural part, and associated logistical activities. The weight of the part plays a pivotal role in raw material extraction and logistics. The efficiency of the manufacturing process, including scrap generation, ratio of faulty parts, and energy and water consumption, is a key focus. Strategies to increase process efficiency include energy-conscious manufacturing, streamlining references, and compatibility with current assembly lines at OEM facilities.

The environmental impact of automotive components is intrinsically linked to their weight due to their direct correlation with the vehicle's energy consumption during its operational phase. While mass-induced fuel consumption (MIF) is comparatively lower in Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs) than in Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) vehicles, it remains a significant factor [15]. Consequently, weight reduction is the principal approach to diminishing the environmental footprint of a vehicle component throughout its usage period.

The structural constituents of an automobile possess the potential for reuse, refurbishment, recycling, or deposition in a landfill upon reaching the end of its life cycle. Each of these end-of-life routes has its own environmental impact, ranging from minimal to significant. However, except for landfill disposal, the least favourable option, the initial step in the process is dismantling. Designing for disassembly is especially important in cases where a vehicle's components consist of multiple materials, as specific joining methods can complicate the sorting process and may even hinder recycling efforts [3].

4 Implementing Material Matrix Metrics

When considering eco-design, designers can make informed choices based on carefully curated parameters that balance ease of assessment with environmental impact relevance. These parameters can be defined based on the project's target. Table 1 depicts examples of the metrics parameter and the weighting factor.

Table 1. An example of the Material Matrix Metrics parameters and the weighting factor.

Metrics parameter	Meaning and method of evaluation
Potential for Weight Reduction	Achieving weight savings is critical for reducing environmental impacts and costs. It is directly linked to energy consumption during production and usage. A simplified assessment using alternative material density is needed, followed by a more precise evaluation tailored to the chosen material and manufacturing.
Process Recyclability	This factor considers the recyclability of the material. It is evaluated on a scale of 1 to 3: 1. "Not recyclable with conventional techniques" 2. "Difficult to recycle with conventional technics." 3. "Easily recyclable".
Assembly/disassembly	the complexity of the assembly/disassembly is related to the lifecycle: production (simple assembly methods increase the manufacturing efficiency), use (to allow maintenance) and end-of-life (to allow easy sorting for reuse, refurbishment, and recycling). 1. "Currently not disassembled, medium complexity for assembly (welding)", 2. "Difficult to assemble/disassemble" (adhesives) 3. "Easily as assemble/disassemble" (bolts)
Reduction of references	integrating different functions in fewer parts contributes to cost-effectiveness and environmental footprint reduction. This metric is measured in terms of the total number of parts saved. The decrease in references can be implanted only by understanding the part's complexity and the manufacturability.
Compatibility with the current assembly line	This metric is evaluated on a scale of 1 to 3: 1. "Significant changes on the assembly line are required" 2. "Minor changes on the assembly line are required." 3. "No changes required".

Let's consider a hypothetical scenario to understand the material matrix's importance in achieving product circularity. Designers need to establish specific criteria for any redesign, such as weight reduction, use of available materials, manufacturability, performance standards, and maintenance facilitation. By following the following steps, a decision can be made efficiently regarding the suitability of different materials for specific subcomponents:

- **Comprehensive Evaluation:** Each design will undergo a thorough assessment based on the established criteria. For example, manufacturability will be assessed in collaboration with part manufacturers and process experts, and crash performance will be simulated to ensure compliance with safety standards.

- **Environmental Assessment:** Designs that successfully meet the predefined criteria will then be subject to an environmental evaluation using specified metrics.
- **Scoring and Weighting:** Ultimately, a score will be assigned to each design in accordance with each category, and these scores will be weighted accordingly.

Then, to calculate the global score of each alternative design, different scores of each parameter will be weighted as per project or condition.

5 Conclusions

In conclusion, this paper investigated the possibilities of redesigning products to align with eco-environmental goals. While the eco-design approaches explored in this study share many commonalities with existing strategies concerning product and material integrity, we introduced a novel and practical tool, the Material Matrix Assessment. The Material Matrix can be used to enhance decision-making when selecting the optimal material for structural components. Our paper not only outlined the concept but also provided a step-by-step procedure for implementing the Material Matrix Metrics, accompanied by an example. By doing so, we aimed to contribute to the growing body of knowledge in eco-design and empower designers and engineers to make more informed choices that can positively impact both the environment and product sustainability.

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